

acetic acid and water (4:1:1, v/v). The chromatograms were air-dried to remove the solvent and cut into consecutive horizontal strips. Each such strip was rendered alkaline with dilute NaOH solution. Within a few seconds the distinct rice like aroma appeared in the strips corresponding to a specific region of the chromatogram, well-separated from ninhydrin-positive spots due to putrescine, cadaverine and phenylethylamine of MF under similar chromatographic conditions. The acidified steam-distillates of MF and rice were spotted and developed side by side on a chromatogram under the same previous conditions. The two aroma regions (MF and rice) coincide and both are ninhydrin-negative.

The 'head space' analysis of MF or its chloroform or hexane or heptane extract was carried out with the help of a Hewlett Packard 5840A dual column analytical gas chromatograph with FID detectors.

MF or chloroform extracts (~2 ml) were taken in screw capped septum vials (3.5 ml) with butyl rubber septum (Pierce, USA) and kept at 30° for 30 min. The 'head space' gas (1 ml), that is the gas above the liquid, was injected into the column and chromatographed using nitrogen as carrier gas. Different samples of MF of two tiggesses and one tiger were used in different seasons. In case of rice, about half of such septum vial was filled with rice, well-moistened with distilled water and kept at 30° for 1 h. The head-space (1 ml) was injected and chromatographed as above. In this way comparison of the glc retention characteristics of the two aroma substances could be made under the same conditions.

The columns chosen for glc analysis were 10% squalane on chromosorb W(HP) (100-12) mesh) and 10% carbowax 20M on chromosorb W(HP) (100-120 mesh) respectively, packed in stainless steel columns (3 m × 3 mm id). Chromatograms were taken at 45° for squalane, and 60° for carbowax columns. The injection port and FID temperature were kept at 20° above column temperature. The carrier gas flow rate was kept at 30 ml min⁻¹. Both MF-head-space and rice-head-space produced one major peak at the identical t_R of 4.8 min on squalane column and a sharper major peak at t_R 2.3 min on carbowax 20M column. Injection of a mixture of the two head-spaces (MF and rice) on the carbowax 20M column resulted in a single peak of t_R 2.3 min. Moreover, injection of head-space of old MF and rice water which have lost the aroma, did not show any such peak.

It thus seems that the fragrant substance in MF is likely to be an organic base which is shared by fragrant varieties of rice.

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Chemical Examination of a Marine Zoanthid of *Gemmaria* sp.

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IN continuation of our study on toxic marine organisms of Visakhapatnam coast^{1,2}, chemical examination of an unidentified *Gemmaria* sp. (Phylum: Coelenterata) is reported here. These animals grow as mats on the intertidal rocks of the Visakhapatnam coast (N 17°, E 83°) and they have a cylindrical structure with a folded bulb-like opening. The animals are attached to the rocky substratum through calcareous matter. The animals (after washing with water) were extracted with aqueous alcohol and subsequent chromatography furnished two compounds A and B.

Compound A analysed for C₂₈H₄₈O, showed the characteristic LB test for sterols. It was found to be transparent in uv (MeOH) and showed ir (KBr) absorption at 3 500 cm⁻¹(OH). It formed a non-acetate (1a) (Ac₂O/Py), C₃₀H₅₀O₂, M⁺ 442, m.p. 133-34°, [α]_D -31.06°; R_f 0.75 (benzene). A comparative study of the ¹H nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of the compound at δ 5.4 (1H, m, C₂-H), 3.43 (1H, m, C₃-H), 1.02 (3H, s, C₁₀-Me), 0.74-0.95 (9H, m, 21, 26 and 27-Me) and 0.7 (3H, s, C₁₄-Me); and its acetate at δ (270 MHz, CDCl₃), 5.38 (1H, m, C₂-H), 4.59 (1H, m, C₃-H), 2.03 (3H, s, C₃-OCOCH₃), 1.02 (3H, s, 19-Me), 0.92 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 21-Me), 0.86 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 26-CH₃), 0.78 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 27-CH₃), 0.78 (3H, d, J 7 Hz,

28-CH₃), 0.68 (3H, s, 18-CH₃), with those of dihydrobrassicasterol and its acetate⁸ revealed its identity as dihydrobrassicasterol (1). The mass fragmentation of its acetate⁸ showed no molecular ion peak but peaks at *m/z* 382 (*M*⁺-60, 100), 367 (17.97), 255 (*M*⁺-60-C₉H₁₆, 18) and 213 (14.91), which further supported its structure.

1; R=H
1a; R=COCH₃

2; R=H
2a; R=COCH₃

Compound B analysed for C₁₁H₁₆O₃, *M*⁺ 196 (15.4%), showed uv (EtOH) absorption at 220 nm for an α,β-unsaturated lactone. Its ir spectrum (KBr) showed bands at 3 445 (OH), 1 740 and 1 625 (α,β-unsaturated-γ-lactone) and 1 380–1 400 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyls). It gave a monoacetate (2a) (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 86°. A comparison of its ¹H nmr spectrum δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 5.62 (1H, s, olefinic proton), 4.28 (1H, m, C₁-H), 1.76 (3H, s, 3-Me), 1.45 (3H, s, 5α-Me), 1.25 (3H, s, 5β-Me), 2.8 (1H, m, 2α-H), 2.0 (1H, m, 2β-H), 1.70 (1H, m, 6α-H) and 1.4 (1H, m, 6β-H), and other physical and spectral characteristics with those of loliolide, suggested the possible identity which was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample⁵.

Lololide has hitherto been reported from plant sources, e.g. from a terrestrial plant *Digitalis purpurea*⁴ and a marine alga, *Padina tetrastrumata* Hauck⁵. It was also reported from *Dolabella ecaudata*⁶ (a sea hare), not very surprisingly, for sea hares are herbivorous and concentrate and store selected algal metabolites in digestive gland from which the metabolites are slowly released⁷. However, its present isolation from a marine animal, a zoanthid of *Gemmaria* sp. appears to be first of its kind.

Experimental

The cleaned animals (7 kg) were percolated with rectified spirit (3 × 5 dm³) and the combined extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a predominantly aqueous suspension (2 dm³). The aqueous concentrate was repeatedly extracted with ether (12 × 50 ml). Evaporation of the ether solvent left a dark green gummy material (10 g), which was

absorbed over silica gel (50 g) and chromatographed over a silica gel (100–200 mesh, 200 g) column using solvents of increasing polarity.

Evaporation of n-hexane–benzene (9:1) fractions left colourless solid, compound A, which was crystallised from methanol as shining needles (2 g), m.p. 148–49°; [α]_D -27.2°; *R*_f 0.52 (C₆H₆-EtOAc, 9:1). Evaporation of benzene-ethyl acetate (95:5) fractions yielded a colourless solid compound B, which was crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 151°; [α]_D -99.0°; *R*_f 0.4 (EtOAc).

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Phenylpropenoid Constituents of *Cymbopogon microstachys*

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CYMOPOGON microstachys (Hook. f.) S. Soenarko has natural occurrence in the Himalayan foothills. This is the first report on existence of this species in this region. Also, no work has been reported on this species so far. The confirmation of the identification has been done by S. Soenarko (who raised this species) in R.B.G., Kew (Herbarium